

Anti-Bacterial Activities of Co-Cd Nano ferrites against the Pathogenic strain of Staphylococcus and E.Coli

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Abstract

This study reports the synthesis and antibacterial assessment of nanostructured $\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (where $x = 0.00, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8,$ and 1.0) spinel ferrite nanoparticles using the citrate gel auto-combustion technique. The substitution of smaller Co^{2+} ions with larger Cd^{2+} ions introduce lattice distortions and macrostrain, which significantly influence antimicrobial activity. These materials were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) strains using minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and optical density (OD) measurements. The results indicate that compositions with balanced cobalt and cadmium ratios particularly $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{Cd}_{0.6}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ exhibited superior antibacterial activity even at low concentrations. The study highlights the role of stress-induced structural modification and cationic distribution in enhancing the biological activity of ferrite nanoparticles, offering promising applications in antimicrobial coatings, environmental disinfection, and biomedical fields.

Key words: Co-Cd nano ferrites, spinel ferrites, Antibacterial activity, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*.

I. Introduction

Ferrites with the general formula AB_2O_4 are an important class of magnetic ceramic materials that adopt a spinel-type crystal structure. In this structure, “A” typically represents a divalent metal ion such as Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , or Mn^{2+} , while “B” is a trivalent metal ion, commonly Fe^{3+} . These ions are embedded in a framework of oxygen atoms (O^{2-}), resulting in a stable cubic or sometimes distorted tetragonal structure. The AB_2O_4 ferrites are known for their ferrimagnetic behaviour, which arises from the distribution of metal ions between two types of interstitial sites in the spinel lattice: tetrahedral (A sites) and octahedral (B sites)[1]. Depending on how the metal ions are arranged, ferrites are classified as normal spinel, inverse spinel, or mixed spinel. In a normal spinel structure, the divalent A ions occupy tetrahedral sites, while the trivalent B ions occupy octahedral sites. In contrast, inverse spinel structures have half of the B ions in tetrahedral sites and the other half along with the A ions in octahedral sites. Mixed spinels exhibit a combination of these distributions[2].

Co-Cd nano ferrites are spinel-structured materials where cobalt (Co^{2+}) and cadmium (Cd^{2+}) ions occupy the tetrahedral (A) and/or octahedral (B) sites of the cubic spinel lattice, alongside iron (Fe^{3+}) ions. In a typical spinel ferrite, the cation distribution and lattice symmetry play a critical role in determining the material's physical and magnetic behaviour[3]. When Co^{2+} ions (which are smaller in size) are partially replaced by larger Cd^{2+} ions, the substitution causes local lattice distortions due to the ionic radius mismatch ($\text{Cd}^{2+} \sim 0.97 \text{ \AA}$ vs. $\text{Co}^{2+} \sim 0.74 \text{ \AA}$). This difference creates internal stress or strain within the spinel framework, as the crystal structure attempts to accommodate the larger Cd^{2+} ions without completely altering the spinel geometry. These distortions, particularly prominent at the nanoscale, result in non-uniform lattice expansion and increased macrostrain, which can be detected through X-ray diffraction (XRD) as broadened and shifted diffraction peaks[4,5].

In the spinel structure, stress typically manifests in the form of tensile or compressive forces acting along the oxygen-metal bonds, altering bond lengths and angles. As Cd^{2+} concentration increases, the lattice constant also increases, indicating an expansion of the unit cell—a direct consequence of stress accumulation within the spinel framework. Such stress is not only a structural phenomenon but also significantly impacts the magnetic and electrical properties of the ferrite. The spinel structure's magnetic behaviour arises from super exchange interactions between Fe^{3+} ions situated at A and B sites[6,7]. When stress modifies the bond angles or distances in these interaction paths, the strength of magnetic coupling can change, leading to variations in saturation magnetization, coercivity, and magnetic anisotropy. For instance, Cd^{2+} ions are non-magnetic and tend to dilute

the magnetic interactions, but the accompanying stress can further reduce the alignment of magnetic domains by disrupting the regular spinel arrangement.

Ferrites, particularly at the nanoscale, have gained significant attention in recent years for their antimicrobial properties. Among them, cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) stands out due to its unique combination of magnetic, surface, and catalytic properties, which make it an effective agent against a broad spectrum of pathogenic microorganisms. The antimicrobial activity of ferrites is primarily attributed to their ability to disrupt microbial cell membranes, generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), and interfere with vital biological processes in microbes[8,9].

Cobalt ferrite has a spinel crystal structure and exhibits strong magnetic behaviour, chemical stability, and mechanical hardness. These characteristics make CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles not only suitable for targeted antimicrobial applications but also easy to recover and reuse due to their magnetic nature. The antibacterial and antifungal effects of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles arise from several mechanisms. First, the nano-size and high surface-to-volume ratio of cobalt ferrite enable them to closely interact with microbial cell walls and membranes, leading to physical damage and leakage of cellular contents[10,11]. This is particularly effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, which have structurally different but vulnerable cell envelopes[12].

Second, cobalt ferrite nanoparticles can generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydroxyl radicals, superoxide anions, and hydrogen peroxide, especially under light exposure or in the presence of certain catalysts. These ROS cause oxidative stress in microbial cells by damaging proteins, lipids, and DNA, eventually leading to cell death[13]. The presence of Co^{2+} ions in the lattice is also believed to play a direct role in microbial toxicity. These ions can interfere with enzyme functions and metabolic processes in bacteria, either by binding to active sites or by replacing essential metal ions such as Mg^{2+} or Zn^{2+} , leading to metabolic disruption and inhibition of cell division[14]. An additional advantage of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles is their reusability and environmental friendliness. After use, they can be magnetically separated, cleaned, and reused, minimizing waste and cost. Unlike conventional antibiotics, which often lead to resistance, the mechanical and oxidative modes of action of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles reduce the risk of developing resistance among pathogens[15].

In this study, we report the synthesis of $\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (where $x = 0.00, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, \text{ and } 1.0$) nanoparticles using the citrate gel auto-combustion method. The antibacterial activity of the synthesized samples was evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* using minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and optical density (OD) measurements.

II. Experimental studies

$\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (where $x = 0.00, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, \text{ and } 1.0$) nanoparticles using the citrate gel auto-combustion method. The detail method of preparation of Co-Cd spinel nano particles process, characterization techniques such as XRD, SEM, EDAX, FTIR, XPS, magnetic and electrical properties have been reported in our **earlier publication**. Dilution methods are the most appropriate for evaluating MIC values since they generate data to estimate the concentration of the tested antimicrobial agent within the broth medium. Dilution methods could also be used to test antimicrobial activity against bacteria in vitro. The lowest concentration of the tested antimicrobial agent that inhibits observable microorganism growth is termed as the Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC). The method involved in preparation of the antimicrobial agent with amounts 0.1mg/mL, 0.2 mg/mL, 0.3mg/mL, 0.4mg/mL and 0.5mg/mL in a liquid broth medium.

500 mL of nutrient broth is prepared followed by sterilisation in autoclave. Two sets (set-1&2) of tubes are arranged, in each set the tubes are designated as 1,2,3,4,5 and 6. 5mL of nutrient broth is dispersed in each tube. Tube number 1 is taken as the blank. The tubes designated with Nos 2,3,4,5 and 6 respectively in each set are added with 0.5mg, 1mg, 1.5mg, 2mg, 2.5mg of nano ferrite of sample SN1 at 37°C. The OD is set to zero in colorimeter at 625 nm in case of first tube (blank) in which no nano ferrite is added. The initial OD is recorded for all the tubes of set-1 and set-2 at 625 nm. 2 μ L of Gram-positive strains of micro-organism *Staphylococcus* is added to each tube of set -1 and 2 μ L of Gram-negative strains of *Escherichia coli* is added to each tube of set-2, including blank and incubated without agitation at 37°C for a period of 24 h. Then the final OD is recorded for the contents of each tube at 625 nm. Based on the OD values recorded calorimetrically the antimicrobial activity of sample SN1 is detected along with the MIC under the experimental conditions. The observed antimicrobial activity of the sample is compared by preparing nutrient agar media and poured on Petri plates allowed for solidification. Then a loop full sample from each tube with different amount of nano ferrite sample

of SN1 inoculated by streak plate method[16–18]. Inoculated plates are incubated in incubator at 37⁰C for 24 hours. After 24 hours observed for formation of colonies. These results are correlated with the results observed calorimetrically.

III. Results and Discussion

A. Anti-microbial activity of Co-Cd nano ferrites

The study aimed to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of synthesized nanostructured ferrite samples (SN1, SN2, SN3, SN4, SN5, and SN6), with varying compositions of cobalt (Co), cadmium (Cd), and iron (Fe), against two model bacterial strains: *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive). **Figure 1** illustrate microbial formation on agar plates for all samples. A visible reduction in cluster density with increasing concentration of SN2–SN5 confirms dose-dependent antimicrobial action. However, the plate for SN6 did not show complete inhibition at any concentration, consistent with its MIC result[19].

Figure 1. Petri plates of inoculated broth with NP of sample SN1, SN2, SN3, SN4, SN5, and SN6.

MIC values offer a quantitative assessment of the lowest concentration required to completely inhibit visible bacterial growth. According to **Tables 1& 2** samples SN1, SN2, SN3, SN4, SN5, and SN6, exhibited complete inhibition of both bacterial strains at the lowest tested concentration of 0.1 mg/mL, highlighting their strong antimicrobial potential. These results corroborate the OD findings and further reinforce that compositions with a balanced **Co-Cd** ratio (particularly SN3) are optimal for antimicrobial applications. On the other hand, SN4 and SN5 showed MIC values of 0.3 mg/mL for both bacteria, indicating they required a higher concentration to be effective. SN6, despite exhibiting low OD values at high concentrations, failed to inhibit bacterial growth completely, and no MIC value could be established for it in the tested range[20]. This suggests that SN6 may act bacterio-statically (inhibiting growth without killing) rather than bactericidally (killing bacteria).

OD measurements reflect bacterial cell density in a given culture medium. Lower OD values indicate less bacterial proliferation, suggesting stronger antimicrobial activity of the nanoparticles. Tables 3 and 4 present OD values for all six samples in nutrient broth, *E. coli*, and *Staphylococcus* environments at various concentrations (0.1–0.5 mg/mL). Among the samples, SN1 (CdFe_2O_4) exhibited the highest OD readings across all concentrations, both for *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus*. This suggests that SN1 has relatively poor antimicrobial properties and is not highly effective in preventing bacterial growth. For example, at 0.5 mg/mL, OD values for SN1 were 1.64 in nutrient broth, 1.66 in *E. coli*, and 1.64 in *Staphylococcus*, which are considerably higher than those recorded for other samples[21]. This indicates that the presence of cadmium alone in the ferrite matrix does not significantly contribute to antibacterial efficacy. In contrast, SN2 ($\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Cd}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) and SN3 ($\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{Cd}_{0.6}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) showed significantly reduced OD values at the same concentrations. Notably, SN3 recorded OD values of 0.61 (*E. coli*) and 0.62 (*Staphylococcus*) at 0.5 mg/mL, indicating effective suppression of microbial growth. These results demonstrate that partial substitution of cadmium with cobalt enhances the antimicrobial activity of the nanoparticles.

Table 1. Schematic representation of MIC values of samples against Gram-negative strain *Staphylococcus*

Series	Staphylococcus					MIC
	1.0×10^{-1} mg/mL	2.0×10^{-1} mg/mL	3.0×10^{-1} mg/mL	4.0×10^{-1} mg/mL	5.0×10^{-1} mg/mL	mg/mL
SN1	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	1.0×10^{-1}
SN2	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	1.0×10^{-1}
SN3	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	1.0×10^{-1}
SN4	N	N	Y	Y	Y	3.0×10^{-1}
SN5	N	N	Y	Y	Y	3.0×10^{-1}
SN6	N	N	N	N	N	-

The improvement can be attributed to cobalt's known role in generating reactive oxygen species (ROS), which damage microbial cell components such as membranes, proteins, and DNA, leading to cell death. As the cobalt content increased further in SN4 ($\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{Cd}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) and SN5 ($\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Cd}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$), OD values increased moderately at lower concentrations but significantly reduced at higher concentrations (0.4–0.5 mg/mL). For instance, SN5 exhibited OD values of 0.27 (*E. coli*) and 0.28 (*Staphylococcus*) at 0.1 mg/mL, which improved to 1.73 and 1.75, respectively, at 0.5 mg/mL. This trend suggests that while these compositions are effective, they require a higher dosage to exert a similar inhibitory effect. This behavior could be explained by nanoparticle aggregation at lower concentrations or reduced bioavailability, necessitating higher dosages to ensure effective antimicrobial action[22]. Interestingly, SN6 (CoFe_2O_4), which contains cobalt exclusively (no cadmium), demonstrated a mixed response. OD values at 0.5 mg/mL were significantly low—1.97 (*E. coli*) and 1.98 (*Staphylococcus*)—indicating suppression of bacterial growth.

Table 2. Schematic representation of MIC values of samples against Gram-positive strain E-coli

Series	E-coli					MIC
	0.1 mg/mL	0.2 mg/mL	0.3 mg/mL	0.4 mg/mL	0.5g/mL	mg/mL
SN1	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	1.0×10^{-1}
SN2	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	1.0×10^{-1}
SN3	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	1.0×10^{-1}
SN4	N	N	Y	Y	Y	3.0×10^{-1}
SN5	N	N	Y	Y	Y	3.0×10^{-1}
SN6	N	N	N	N	N	-

Table 3. Measured OD values of samples (SN-1, SN-2 & SN-3) in presence of broth at various dilutions

Amount of Sample mg/mL	OD measured (SN-1)			OD measured (SN-2)			OD measured (SN-3)		
	Nutrient Broth	E.Coli	Staphylo-coccus	Nutrient Broth	E.Coli	Staphylo-coccus	Nutrient Broth	E.Coli	Staphylo-coccus
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.1	0.42	0.41	0.43	0.12	0.11	0.1	0.08	0.09	0.1
0.2	0.52	0.5	0.51	0.26	0.25	0.27	0.15	0.16	0.16
0.3	0.7	0.69	0.721	0.52	0.51	0.53	0.28	0.29	0.28
0.4	1.35	1.35	1.35	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.47	0.48	0.49
0.5	1.64	1.66	1.64	1.16	1.17	1.16	0.61	0.63	0.62

Table 4. Measured OD values of samples (SN-4, SN-5&SN-6) in presence of broth at various amounts of Nano Ferrite sample.

amount of Sample mg/mL	OD measured (SN-4)			OD measured (SN-5)			OD measured (SN-6)		
	Nutrient Broth	E.Coli	Staphylo-coccus	Nutrient Broth	E.Coli	Staphylo-coccus	Nutrient Broth	E.Coli	Staphylo-coccus
0	0			0			0		
0.1	0.39	0.45	0.55	0.21	0.27	0.28	0.11	0.35	0.43
0.2	0.71	0.77	0.77	0.38	0.4	0.56	0.23	0.38	0.51
0.3	1.24	1.25	1.27	0.42	0.48	0.49	0.44	0.55	1.04
0.4	1.68	1.7	1.69	1.35	1.42	1.45	1.28	1.58	1.77
0.5	1.85	1.86	1.85	1.65	1.73	1.75	1.66	1.97	1.98

IV. Conclusion

The findings of this research confirm that the antimicrobial activity of Co-Cd ferrite nanoparticles is highly dependent on the Co: Cd ratio in the spinel structure. Among the six compositions tested, Co_{0.4}Cd_{0.6}Fe₂O₄ (SN3) exhibited the most effective inhibition against both *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, even at low concentrations. This optimal performance is attributed to the enhanced generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and efficient interactions with microbial membranes, enabled by the balanced cationic configuration and induced lattice strain. Samples with extreme compositions, such as SN1 (CdFe₂O₄) and SN6 (CoFe₂O₄), were comparatively less effective, with SN6 acting primarily as a bacteriostatic agent. These results suggest that fine-tuning the metal ion ratio in spinel ferrites can lead to the development of potent, reusable, and environmentally friendly antimicrobial nanomaterials.

V. References

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